

The Dial-a-Ride Problem with Meeting Points: A Problem Formulation for Shared Demand-Responsive Transit

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Abstract

In this paper, a formulation for the Dial-a-Ride Problem with Meeting Points (DARPmp) is introduced. The problem consists of defining routes that satisfy trip requests between pick-up and drop-off points while complying with time window, ride time, vehicle load, and route duration constraints. A set of meeting points is defined, and passengers may be asked to use these meeting points as alternative pickup or drop-off points if this results in routes with lower costs. Incorporating meeting points into the DARP is achieved by formulating a mixed-integer linear program. Two preprocessing steps and three valid inequalities are introduced, which improve the computational performance when solving the DARPmp to global optimality. Two versions of the Tabu Search metaheuristic are proposed to approximate the optimal solution in large-scale networks due to the NP-hardness of DARPmp. Performing numerical experiments with benchmark instances, this study demonstrates the benefits of DARPmp compared to DARP in terms of reducing vehicle running costs.

Keywords: Dial-a-Ride Problem, Meeting Points, Demand Responsive Transit, Tabu Search

1. Introduction

Demand-Responsive Transit (DRT) is a relatively new mobility concept that distinguishes itself from public transit by providing flexible arrival and departure times and flexible routes, whereas public transit has fixed timetables and fixed routes. Major developments in communication technology in the past years, like the incorporation of GPS and access to wireless internet for cell phones, have allowed access to online information and the location of travelers. These developments make this type of transport more accessible for everyone (Masoud and Jayakrishnan, 2017). There are several providers that make DRT possible, from conventional taxi services to companies like Uber and Lyft. A shortcoming of these DRT services is that they can cause an increase in the number of cars on the road. Trips that were previously made by public transport are replaced by trips in non-shared vehicles (Tirachini and Gomez-Lobo, 2020; Gkiotsalitis, 2022). Therefore, the incorporation of ride-sharing in these DRT systems has been proposed. In a ride-sharing system, travelers with somewhat similar routes and time schedules share a vehicle to get from their origin to their destination. There are several types of ride-sharing, like carpooling, vanpooling, or shared taxis (Mourad et al., 2019). When properly executed, ride-sharing can have many advantages for society as well as for individual users. Sharing a car results in fewer vehicles on the road and a reduction of the distance traveled by cars, resulting in a reduction of fuel consumption (Jacobsen and King,

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2009). Fewer vehicles on the road can also reduce congestion problems (Chen et al., 2019). For individual travelers, sharing a ride can be attractive since their travel costs for gas, tolls, or parking fees can be reduced because they are split over several people (Furuhata et al., 2013). The expectation is that the use of these demand-responsive ride-sharing services will increase over the coming years because there is a desire to mitigate the climate effects of transportation.

A disadvantage of the application of ride-sharing is that passengers are often picked up and dropped off door-to-door. When multiple people share a vehicle, this can result in vehicles having to make detours from the shortest path to pickup and drop off passengers, possibly through slow streets (Fielbaum et al., 2021). This problem could be avoided if passengers are asked to walk a short distance from their origin to their pickup location and from their drop off location to their destination. These alternative pickup and delivery locations are referred to as meeting points. Several studies have shown that introducing meeting points in these ride-sharing systems reduces costs in terms of travel time and travel distance (Stiglic et al., 2015; Fielbaum et al., 2021). Figure 1 shows an example of a network with meeting points. The figure shows a tour without meeting points on the left and with meeting points on the right. In the tour in the left part of the figure, some detours are made to pick up and drop off all passengers. The tour in the right part of the figure has meeting points included, and it shows a more direct route to the destination.

Figure 1: Meeting points in a traffic network

Given the compelling nature of evaluating the impact of ride-sharing services on a traffic network and formulating optimal scheduling strategies, various optimization problems have been developed. Among these formulations, the Dial-a-Ride problem (DARP) stands out. Initially applied for the door-to-door transportation of disabled and elderly individuals, the DARP offers a framework to devise efficient vehicle routes and schedules that cater to specific trip requests. This involves the designated pickup and drop-off points of individual travellers. The overarching objective of this approach is to meticulously plan routes by optimally deploying multiple vehicles (Cordeau and Laporte, 2007). This problem framework resonates with the ride-sharing Demand-Responsive Transportation (DRT) services, as these services similarly handle travel requests where passengers seek shared transport between origin and destination points.

The DARP includes static and dynamic formulations, where all travel requests are predetermined and where requests progressively unfold throughout the day, respectively (Cordeau and Laporte, 2007). Moreover, extensions of this model have been proposed. Notably, some extensions incorporate transfer possibilities (Masson et al., 2014), while others integrate battery swapping stations tailored for electric vehicles (Masmoudi et al., 2018). Building upon the latter, a novel extension could involve the integration of the previously mentioned meeting points. This would entail identifying optimal meeting points for trip requests in tandem with devising the most efficient routes, thereby enhancing the overall operational effectiveness of the model.

The aim of this research is to extend the DARP to include meeting points. This new formulation will be referred to as the Dial-a-Ride Problem with meeting points (DARPmp). This study centers around addressing a pivotal research inquiry: how can the DARP be

effectively expanded to incorporate the identification of optimal meeting points, all the while devising routes that are optimally efficient.

The contribution of this research is the extension of the DARP in a way that it includes meeting points. This means that the optimal meeting point for a request is found while solving the DARPmp, instead of first defining a meeting point for certain requests and then solving the original DARP. The contribution consists of the formulation of a mixed-integer non-linear program for DARPmp and the linearization of this problem formulation to get a mixed-integer linear program that can be solved to global optimality. It also consists of the formulation of a number of preprocessing steps and valid inequalities for the DARPmp to reduce the search of the solution space. Next to that, two meta-heuristic algorithms are proposed to solve the DARPmp for large instances.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In section 2, a literature review about the DARP and meeting points is provided. In section 3, the classic formulation of the DARP is presented. In section 4, a mixed-integer non-linear program is proposed for the DARPmp, which is linearized to a mixed-integer linear program. In this section, the sets, parameters, variables, constraints and valid inequalities are described. In section 5, two meta-heuristics are proposed to approximate the optimal solution of the DARPmp for large problem instances. In section 6, the application of the DARPmp to a small network is demonstrated, and the setup and results of the numerical experiments regarding the preprocessing steps and valid inequalities, the exact model and the two meta-heuristics are presented. The study ends with section 7, which provides a discussion and future research directions.

2. Literature review

2.1. Dial-A-Ride Problem

The DARP is used to design vehicle routes and schedules for travellers that have specific trip requests from certain origins to certain destinations (Cordeau and Laporte, 2007; Gkiotsalitis, 2021; Gkiotsalitis and Nikolopoulou, 2023). In the most standard form, the trips can be supplied by a fleet of homogeneous vehicles that originate from and return to the same depot. The input for this problem consists of a traffic network represented by a directed graph with corresponding costs and travel times to traverse the arcs. Furthermore there is a capacity for the vehicles and time restrictions for the operation of the vehicles. Next to that there is a set of trip requests from users that want to travel from an origin to a destination. These requests have some characteristics, like a time window for pickup and drop off for example.

The DARP originates from routing problems, such as the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) and the Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem (CVRP). The TSP consists of a single vehicle that has to visit all given cities, using the shortest possible route. In the CVRP the aim is to find optimal routes for picking up and delivering certain goods with a limited number of vehicles that have a limited capacity (Gambella et al., 2018). The DARP is also similar to another problem, which is called the Pickup and Delivery Vehicle Routing Problem (PDVRP) (Cordeau and Laporte, 2007). The PDVRP concerns the transportation of goods from a certain origin to a certain destination. The transportation of goods has different characteristics than the transportation of persons. Goods can, for example, be stalled at some place for a certain time or travel to some place with a large detour, while this is not tolerable for the transportation of persons.

The DARP has garnered extensive research attention, leading to the exploration of numerous extensions and variations. Among these extensions is the DARP with multiple depots and a heterogeneous fleet of vehicles. This version introduces diversified vehicle characteristics, incorporating factors like capacity and depot location (Braekers et al., 2014; Masmoudi

et al., 2016; Malheiros et al., 2021). Additionally, variants of the DARP have been devised to incorporate transfer opportunities between distinct vehicles. Such adaptations contribute to route schedules with reduced travel costs (Masson et al., 2014; Pierotti and van Essen, 2021). As the landscape evolves with the rise of electric vehicles (EVs), novel problem formulations have arisen. These formulations highlight the limitation of EVs requiring intermittent charging, a process that consumes more time than conventional refueling. In this context, research has proposed versions of the DARP tailored for electric vehicles (Masmoudi et al., 2018; Ma, 2021; Bongiovanni et al., 2019). An additional emerging trend is the integration of autonomous vehicles, which are free from driver-related constraints. Consequently, various formulations of the DARP have been developed to accommodate autonomous vehicles (Pimenta et al., 2017; Johnsen and Meisel, 2022; Bongiovanni et al., 2019). This new perspective capitalizes on the unique capabilities offered by driverless vehicles.

In addition to the diverse extensions and variants, the realm of the Dial-a-Ride Problem (DARP) is enriched by various solution methodologies. Since the problem becomes harder to solve when the number of trip requests increases, many studies are performed that aim to reduce the computation time for finding an optimal solution for the DARP. Cordeau and Laporte (2003), for example, proposed a Tabu Search heuristic for the static multi-vehicle DARP. Cordeau (2006) used new valid inequalities in a Branch-and-cut algorithm, reducing the CPU time and the number of nodes explored in the Branch-and-bound tree. A Granular Tabu Search algorithm for the DARP is proposed by Kirchler and Calvo (2013) to produce good solutions for the DARP within 3 minutes. In the study performed by Braekers et al. (2014), a Branch-and-cut algorithm was adapted to solve the Multi-Depot Heterogeneous DARP for small instances, and a Deterministic Annealing meta-heuristic was proposed to solve larger instances. Masmoudi et al. (2017) used a Genetic Algorithm combining a construction heuristic, crossover operators and local search techniques to find a good solution for the Heterogeneous DARP. An improved Tabu Search heuristic was proposed by Ho et al. (2018) to find an improved solution for the static DARP. Using a construction heuristic and time window adjustments, a faster convergence to the optimal solution was observed.

2.2. Meeting points

One of the challenges associated with DRT services in which ride-sharing is used, is the potential for extended detours and increased travel time for passengers, resulting from the multiple pick-ups and drop-offs of other passengers. This issue is not only disadvantageous from the passengers' perspective but also undermines operational efficiency for service providers, as routes become less streamlined with the inclusion of significant detours. For this reason, the concept of meeting points is introduced. Meeting points are alternative pickup or drop off locations situated within walking distance from a traveler's origin or destination. The introduction of meeting points offers a compelling remedy, as it helps mitigate the detour-related challenges. Notably, the implementation of meeting points has shown to foster increased alignment between drivers and riders, subsequently reducing travel costs associated with lengthy detours (Stiglic et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2019; Fielbaum et al., 2021).

Several past studies are dedicated to optimizing vehicle routes while leveraging the concept of meeting points. Chen et al. (2019) proposed an innovative approach involving an integer linear program tailored for the ride-sharing problem, encompassing return restrictions, meeting points, and transfer options. This model is tailored to address the commuting and business traffic within a confined community of companies. The identification of meeting points is achieved through the intersection of potential time intervals for users. This approach signifies the feasible timeframe during which a passenger can be available at a specific node. When the time intervals of two requests intersect and a shared node on their paths can be identified, a meeting point is established to serve both requests effectively. Similarly, Fiel-

baum et al. (2021) devised a ride-sharing system whereby passengers are encouraged to walk to a designated pickup location or from a drop-off point to their destination. Feasible meeting points are identified via a meticulous adherence to constraints, incorporating factors like maximum walking time and ensuring passengers have adequate time to walk to the meeting point. Their solution employs a heuristic strategy to address intricate versions of the problem. Applying their model to a real case in Manhattan, their findings indicate that short walks can significantly enhance the system by reducing vehicle-hours-travelled. Furthermore, Stiglic et al. (2015) investigated the benefits of meeting points by using a maximum weight bipartite matching problem formulation, which was extended to account for single driver, multiple rider characteristics. They designed an algorithm that matches drivers and riders in large scale systems and found that introducing meeting points saves travel costs and increases the number of matched participants.

Finally, there is also a study that uses meeting points in DARP. Gökay (2021) studied various forms of the DARP and applied it to both a rural area with low demand and urban areas with high demand. He investigated the possibility to expand the model by trying to reduce small detours of the vehicles by adding meeting points. This was done by analysing historical demand data to determine hot spots that can be used as pickup or drop off locations. These virtual stations can be different in time. After these locations have been determined, the regular DARP was solved. Meeting points have been recently introduced in other problems, such as the CVRP (Zhang et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023) and the semi-flexible route transit problems (Zhang et al., 2023; Li et al., 2023).

2.3. Literature overview

An overview of the literature used for this study is presented in Table 1. The studies regarding the DARP and its extensions and variants are listed in this table. The studies are presented with their corresponding base model, extension, objective, solution method and formulation type. For the base model, a distinction is made between the DARP and other models. For the extension of the models, a distinction is made between transfers (TF), Multi-Depot and Heterogeneous vehicles (MDH), Electric Vehicles (EV), Autonomous Vehicles (AUT) and Meeting Points (MP). Regarding the objective function, minimizing the travel costs (MTC) and minimizing the ride time for passengers (MRT) form the main categories. Models with another objective function fall in the category ‘other’. For the solution method, a distinction is made between exact methods, i.e., Branch-and-Cut (B&C) and Brand-and-Bound (B&B), and (meta)heuristics. For the meta-heuristics, a column is made for Tabu Search (TS), Genetic Algorithms (GA), Simulated or Deterministic Annealing (S/DA). All other meta-heuristics fall in the category ‘other’. For the formulation type, a distinction is made between an Integer Linear Program (ILP) and a Mixed-Integer Linear Program (MILP). In the last row of this table, the characteristics of this work are presented. Compared to past studies, this work is the first that incorporates the optimal selection of meeting points to the formulation of DARP and solves the resulting DARPmp in one stage, instead of selecting the meeting points in advance and solving the DARP independently (i.e., at a second stage). This incorporation of the meeting points to the problem’s formulation results in finding better solutions compared to myopic approaches which do not include the selection of meeting points as part of the optimization process. Summarizing, the main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- the development of a mathematical model which incorporates the selection of meeting points to the DARP formulation.
- the reformulation of the developed model as a MILP that can be solved to global optimality.

- the reduction of the computational complexity of the model by introducing problem-specific preprocessing steps and valid inequalities, allowing to solve larger network instances.
- the introduction of a method for generating an initial pool of meeting points.
- the introduction of problem-specific Tabu search metaheuristics for obtaining solutions in larger networks.
- the analysis of the performance of the proposed method against classic DARP formulations in benchmark problem instances, demonstrating vehicle running cost improvements of up to 3% in scenarios with up to 24 requests.

Table 1: Literature review

Author	Base Model		Extension					Objective			Exact			Meta-Heuristic				Formulation	
	DARP	Other	TF	MDH	EV	AUT	MP	MTC	MRT	Other	B&C	B&B	Other	TS	GA	S/DA	Other	ILP	MILP
Cordeau and Laporte (2003)	✓							✓						✓					
Cordeau (2006)	✓							✓			✓								✓
Kirchler and Calvo (2013)	✓							✓						✓					✓
Braekers et al. (2014)	✓				✓			✓			✓				✓				✓
Masson et al. (2014)			✓						✓								✓		✓
Stiglic et al. (2015)		✓					✓	✓	✓			✓							✓
Masmoudi et al. (2016)	✓			✓				✓									✓		
Masmoudi et al. (2017)	✓							✓						✓					✓
Pimenta et al. (2017)	✓				✓	✓			✓								✓	✓	
Ho et al. (2018)	✓							✓						✓					✓
Masmoudi et al. (2018)	✓				✓			✓									✓		✓
Bongiovanni et al. (2019)	✓				✓	✓		✓	✓		✓								✓
Chen et al. (2019)		✓	✓				✓		✓			✓					✓	✓	
Fielbaum et al. (2021)		✓					✓	✓	✓			✓					✓	✓	
Gökay (2021)	✓						✓	✓									✓		
Ma (2021)	✓				✓				✓								✓		✓
Malheiros et al. (2021)	✓			✓				✓									✓		✓
Pierotti and van Essen (2021)	✓		✓					✓			✓							✓	
Johnsen and Meisel (2022)	✓					✓		✓									✓		✓
This work	✓						✓	✓			✓		✓						✓

3. The Dial-a-Ride Problem

In this section, the three-index formulation of Cordeau (2006) is briefly presented. This formulation is used in the remainder of this study as the classic formulation of DARP. This formulation aims to minimize the costs of routes that complete all trip requests. The problem formulation consists of several sets. The problem is formulated on a directed graph $G = (V, A)$, where V is the set of vertices and A is the set of arcs (also known as directed edges). The set V of vertices can be partitioned into three sets, being the set of pickup nodes $P = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, the set of delivery nodes $D = \{n + 1, n + 2, \dots, 2n\}$ and the set of depots, which is denoted as $\{0, 2n + 1\}$, containing two copies of the depot. The sets of pickup and delivery vertices are ordered in such a way that each trip request is coupled as $(i, n + i)$, in which i is the pickup vertex and $n + i$ is the corresponding drop off vertex. In the case that two passengers have the same pickup location but a different drop off location, the corresponding pickup vertex is duplicated. The same holds if two passengers have the same drop off point but another origin. In this case, the drop off point is duplicated. When there are multiple passengers that have the same origin-destination pair, the request of these passengers is represented by a pickup and drop off pair. In this case, each pickup vertex i is coupled to drop off vertex $n + i$, which are associated with one origin-destination pair. The

arcs in the set A consist of all outgoing arcs from the depot $\{(0, j) : j \in P\}$, all returning arcs to the depot $\{(i, 2n+1) : i \in D\}$ and all arcs between pickup and delivery nodes $\{(i, j) : i \in P \cup D, j \in P \cup D, i \neq j, i \neq n+j\}$. Lastly, there is a set K consisting of all available vehicles.

Herein, we also present the parameters of the problem. The cost of traveling arcs $(i, j) \in A$ is given by c_{ij}^k , where k represents the vehicle. The travel time over these arcs is given by t_{ij} . Each vehicle has a ride time that cannot exceed the maximum route duration denoted by T_k and a vehicle capacity Q_k that cannot be exceeded. Every vertex has a corresponding time window in which a passenger needs to be picked up or dropped off, denoted by $[e_i, l_i]$. Next to this time window, each vertex also has a service duration $d_i \geq 0$ where the service duration for the depot equals 0. Each vertex also has an associated passenger load $q_i \geq 0$. For the depots, $q_0 = q_{2n+1} = 0$. The pickup and delivery passenger loads are associated such that $q_{n+i} = -q_i$. For each passenger, the maximum allowed ride time is L .

Four sets of variables are used in this model. First, variables $x_{ij}^k \in \{0, 1\}$ for $(i, j) \in A$, $k \in K$ are used to indicate if arc (i, j) is traversed by vehicle k or not. Next, variables $u_i^k \in \mathbb{N}$ for $i \in V$, $k \in K$ are used to indicate the time at which vehicle k starts serving node i . Furthermore, variables $w_i^k \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ for $i \in V$, $k \in K$ are used to update the load of vehicle k when leaving node i . Lastly, variables $r_i^k \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ for $i \in V$, $k \in K$ indicate the ride time of the passenger corresponding to request $(i, n+i)$ on vehicle k .

$$\min \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{(i,j) \in A} c_{ij}^k x_{ij}^k \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{j:(i,j) \in A} x_{ij}^k = 1, \quad \forall i \in P \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{j \in P} x_{0j}^k = \sum_{i \in D} x_{i,2n+1}^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{j:(i,j) \in A} x_{ij}^k - \sum_{j:(i,j) \in A} x_{n+i,j}^k = 0 \quad i \in P, k \in K \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{j:(j,i) \in A} x_{ji}^k - \sum_{j:(i,j) \in A} x_{i,j}^k = 0 \quad \forall i \in P \cup D, k \in K \quad (5)$$

$$u_j^k \geq (u_i^k + d_i + t_{ij})x_{ij}^k \quad \forall (i, j) \in A, k \in K \quad (6)$$

$$w_j^k \geq (w_i^k + q_j)x_{ij}^k \quad \forall (i, j) \in A, k \in K \quad (7)$$

$$r_i^k = u_{n+i}^k - (u_i^k + d_i) \quad i \in P, k \in K \quad (8)$$

$$u_{2n+1}^k - u_0^k \leq T_k \quad \forall k \in K \quad (9)$$

$$e_i \leq u_i^k \leq l_i \quad \forall i \in V, k \in K \quad (10)$$

$$t_{i,n+i} \leq r_i^k \leq L \quad \forall i \in P, k \in K \quad (11)$$

$$\max\{0, q_i\} \leq w_i^k \leq \min\{Q_k, Q_k + q_i\} \quad \forall i \in V, k \in K \quad (12)$$

$$x_{ij}^k \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall (i, j) \in A, k \in K \quad (13)$$

Constraints (2) and (4) ensure that each pickup is carried out exactly once and that each pickup and delivery combination will be served by the same vehicle. Constraints (5) are the flow conservation constraints. When combined with constraints (3), they ensure that each route will start and end at the depot. Constraints (6) ensure the time dimension is respected, so when arc (i, j) is traversed by vehicle k , the time the vehicle starts its service at vertex j is greater than or equal to the start time at node i plus the service time at node i and the travel time between vertex i and vertex j . Constraints (7) ensure that the load of the vehicle is updated correctly. Constraints (8) ensure that the ride time of each passenger is saved in the

correct way, including the service time at the pickup location and the start time of serving vertex i and the start time of serving vertex $i + n$. Constraints (9) ensure that the ride time of a vehicle does not exceed the maximal route duration and constraints (10) guarantee that all pickups and drop offs occur in their corresponding time window. Constraints (11) ensure that the maximal ride time per passenger is not exceeded, and constraints (12) ensure that the capacity of the vehicle is not exceeded.

The classic formulation of the DARP contains two constraints, being (6) and (7), which are not affine functions and make the problem formulation non-linear. Cordeau (2006) proposed to replace these constraints by the affine inequality constraints (14) and (15), making the model linear.

$$u_j^k \geq u_i^k + d_i + t_{ij} - M_{ij}^k(1 - x_{ij}^k) \quad \forall (i, j) \in A, k \in K \quad (14)$$

$$w_j^k \geq w_i^k + q_j - W_{ij}^k(1 - x_{ij}^k) \quad \forall (i, j) \in A, k \in K \quad (15)$$

In these constraints, M_{ij}^k are parameters which should be greater than $\max\{0, l_i + d_i + t_{ij} - e_j\}$ and W_{ij}^k are also parameters which should be greater than $\min\{Q_k, Q_k + q_i\}$.

4. Dial-a-Ride Problem with Meeting Points

4.1. Sets

In the DARPmp, there are n trip requests, where a request couple is referred to as $(i, n + i)$. There is a set K , containing all available vehicles. Next, let $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A})$ be a directed graph. The vertex set of the graph \mathcal{N} can be partitioned into $\{\{0, 2n + 1\}, P, D, \mathcal{M}\}$. Here, the set $\{0, 2n + 1\}$ contains two copies of the depot. The set $P = \{1, \dots, n\}$ contains all pick up vertices and the set $D = \{n + 1, \dots, 2n\}$ contains all drop off vertices. The set $\mathcal{M} = \{2n + 2, \dots, |\mathcal{N}|\}$ contains all possible meeting points. The set of meeting points \mathcal{M} has two subsets, being the subset with meeting points that are within reach for a pick up vertex \mathcal{M}_p and the subset with meeting points that are within reach for a drop off vertex \mathcal{M}_d . These two sets do not have to be distinct, i.e., they might have the same vertices. The set that indicates all vertices in the original network that does not include meeting points is referred to as $V = \{P \cup D \cup \{0, 2n + 1\}\}$. The arc set \mathcal{A} contains the following arcs:

- All outgoing arcs from the depot to pick up vertices and pickup meeting points $\{(0, j) : j \in P \cup \mathcal{M}_p\}$
- All arcs going from a delivery vertex or a delivery meeting point to the depot $\{(i, 2n + 1) : i \in D \cup \mathcal{M}_d\}$
- All arcs between pick up and drop off vertices $\{(i, j) : i \in P \cup D, j \in P \cup D, i \neq j, i \neq n + j\}$
- All arcs going from pick up and delivery nodes to meeting point vertices $\{(i, j) : i \in P \cup D, j \in \mathcal{M}\}$
- All arcs going from meeting points to pickup and delivery vertices $\{(i, j) : i \in \mathcal{M}, j \in P \cup D\}$
- All arcs between meeting points $\{(i, j) : i \in \mathcal{M}, j \in \mathcal{M}, i \neq j\}$

An example of how a graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A})$ is structured is given in Figure 2. In this example, there are two requests and two meeting points, where $P = \{1, 2\}$, $D = \{3, 4\}$, $\mathcal{M} = \{6, 7\}$, $\mathcal{M}_p = \{6\}$ and $\mathcal{M}_d = \{7\}$. It is important to note that vertices 0 and 5 represent the depot and are actually at the same physical location. However, for the sake of enhancing comprehension of the illustration, they are portrayed as distinct locations. Arcs that also exist in the original DARP are grey, new arcs are black, pick up and delivery vertices are blue and meeting points are orange.

Figure 2: Structure of the graph \mathcal{G} with meeting points

Figure 2a shows the graph for the original DARP. Figure 2b shows the new graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A})$ with all arcs included. All other sub-figures show a subset of the arcs to give more insight in what the description of arcs given above means. Figure 2c shows all arcs going from and to the depot, 2d shows all arcs going between pick up and delivery vertices, 2e shows all arcs going between pick up and delivery vertices and meeting points and vice versa, and 2f shows all arcs going between all meeting points.

4.2. Parameters

Each arc $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$ has an associated cost c_{ij}^k when traversed by vehicle k and an associated travel time t_{ij} . Each vehicle cannot exceed the route duration denoted by T_k and can also not exceed their capacity Q_k , where $k \in K$. Each vertex $i \in V$ has a service duration d_i , where $d_i \geq 0$ and $d_0 = d_{2n+1} = 0$. Each vertex has also a passenger load q_i , where $q_i \geq 0$ for $i \in P$. For the delivery vertices $q_{n+i} = -q_i$. Each vertex $i \in V$ has associated time windows $[e_i, l_i]$ and the maximum ride time for passengers is referred to as L .

The meeting point vertices lack fixed time windows, predefined service durations, or specified passenger loads. This is attributed to the inherent uncertainty surrounding the pairing of requests with specific meeting points. As the correspondence between requests and meeting points remains uncertain until later stages, these parameters remain undefined for the meeting point vertices. To assign these values to the meeting points, several variables and constraints are used which are explained in the next sections. Furthermore, some new parameters are introduced. The maximum walking distance from a vertex to a meeting point or from a meeting point to a vertex is C^{max} . The walking time between vertices is referred to as p_{ij} for $i, j \in \mathcal{N}$. Lastly, the maximum tolerated walking time for a passenger to/from a meeting point is given by W .

4.3. Variables

A binary variable $x_{ij}^k \in \{0, 1\}$ is used to indicate whether a vehicle $k \in K$ traverses an arc $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$. $u_i^k \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is a continuous variable that is used to indicate the time at which

vehicle $k \in K$ starts servicing vertex $i \in \mathcal{N}$. $w_i^k \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is used to update the load of vehicle $k \in K$ when leaving vertex $i \in \mathcal{N}$. In the original DARP, variable $r_i^k \in \mathbb{N}$ for $i \in V$, $k \in K$ is used to indicate the ride time of the passenger corresponding to request $(i, n+i)$ on vehicle k . In the DARPmp, the ride time is not captured in a variable, but it is bounded with the use of additional constraints. This is explained in section 4.4.

Moreover, four new sets of variables are introduced. The first variable is a binary variable $y_{ij}^k \in \{0, 1\}$ which is used to indicate if vertex $i \in V$ is coupled to a pickup/delivery point or a meeting point $j \in \mathcal{N}$ for vehicle $k \in K$. Note that a vertex can also be coupled to itself, which would mean in practice that no meeting point is used for this vertex. It can also be coupled to a vertex that is in the sets P or D , which means means again that no meeting point is used for this vertex. Next, there are two variables that are used to assign the flexible passenger demand and service duration to a serviced point. The first variable is $z_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}$ for $i \in V, j \in \mathcal{N}$ which is used to couple the passenger demand from request i to point j if vertex i is coupled to point j . The second variable is $s_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}$ for $i \in V, j \in \mathcal{N}$ which is used to couple the service duration from vertex i to point j , if i and j are coupled. Lastly, a variable to indicate the total walking time of a passenger is used, which is $v_i^k \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ for $i \in V$ for $k \in K$.

4.4. Mathematical formulation

In this section, the objective function and constraints of the DARPmp are presented and described. The mathematical formulation for the DARPmp is defined as follows:

$$\min \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} c_{ij}^k x_{ij}^k \quad (16)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_{ij}^k = 1, \quad \forall i \in P \cup D \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{j:(j,l) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{jl}^k \geq y_{il}^k \quad \forall i \in V, l \in \mathcal{N}, k \in K \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{j \in P \cup \mathcal{M}_p} x_{0j}^k = \sum_{i \in D \cup \mathcal{M}_d} x_{i,2n+1}^k = 1 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{j:(j,i) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ji}^k - \sum_{j:(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ij}^k = 0 \quad \forall i \in P \cup D \cup \mathcal{M}, k \in K \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_{ij}^k - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_{n+i,j}^k = 0 \quad \forall i \in P, k \in K \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{i \in V} y_{ij}^k \geq 1 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (22)$$

$$y_{ij}^k + y_{i+n,j}^k \leq 1 \quad \forall i \in P, k \in K, j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (23)$$

$$s_{ij} = \sum_{k \in K} y_{ij}^k d_i \quad \forall i \in P \cup D, j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (24)$$

$$z_{ij} = \sum_{k \in K} y_{ij}^k q_i \quad \forall i \in P \cup D, j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (25)$$

$$u_j^k \geq (u_i^k + t_{ij} + \sum_{l \in V} s_{li}) x_{ij}^k \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{A}, k \in K \quad (26)$$

$$w_j^k \geq (w_i^k + \sum_{l \in V} z_{lj}) x_{ij}^k \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{A}, k \in K \quad (27)$$

$$w_0^k = w_{2n+1}^k = 0 \quad \forall k \in K \quad (28)$$

$$u_{2n+1}^k - u_0^k \leq T_k \quad \forall k \in K \quad (29)$$

$$(e_i + p_{ij})y_{ij}^k \leq u_j^k \leq l_i + (1 - y_{ij}^k)T_k \quad \forall i \in P, j \in \mathcal{N}, k \in K \quad (30)$$

$$e_i y_{ij}^k \leq u_j^k \leq l_i - p_{ij} + (1 - y_{ij}^k)T_k \quad \forall i \in D, j \in \mathcal{N}, k \in K \quad (31)$$

$$\sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}} y_{i+n,l}^k u_l^k - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (y_{i,j}^k (u_j^k + \sum_{i \in V} s_{ij})) \leq L \quad \forall i \in P, k \in K \quad (32)$$

$$t_{j,l} \leq \sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}} y_{i+n,l}^k u_l^k - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (y_{i,j}^k (u_j^k + \sum_{i \in V} s_{ij})) \quad \forall i \in P, k \in K \quad (33)$$

$$\max\{0, \sum_{i \in V} z_{ij}\} \leq w_j^k \leq \min\{Q_k, Q_k + \sum_{i \in V} z_{ij}\} \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}, k \in K \quad (34)$$

$$c_{ij} y_{ij}^k \leq C^{max} \quad \forall i \in V, j \in \mathcal{N}, k \in K \quad (35)$$

$$v_i^k = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_{ij}^k p_{ij} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_{i+n,j} p_{i+n,j} \quad \forall i \in P, k \in K \quad (36)$$

$$v_i^k \leq W \quad \forall i \in P, k \in K \quad (37)$$

$$x_{ij}^k \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}, k \in K \quad (38)$$

$$y_{ij}^k \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in V, j \in \mathcal{N}, k \in K \quad (39)$$

$$z_{ij}, s_{ij} \in \mathbb{R} \quad \forall i \in V, j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (40)$$

The objective function (16) aims to minimize the total travel costs. Constraints (17) ensure that each pick up or delivery vertex is coupled to one, and only one point, being itself or another vertex. Constraints (18) guarantee that when a vertex is coupled to a point, a vehicle drives to that point. With constraints (19), each vehicle starts at the depot and ends at the depot. Constraints (20) are the flow conservation constraints, that ensure that a vehicle can only drive to a vertex if it also leaves this vertex. These constraints do not hold for the depot vertices. To ensure that a passenger is picked up and dropped off by the same vehicle, constraints (21) are included. Constraints (22) ensure that each vehicle fulfills at least one passenger request, to prevent that a vehicle only drives to a meeting point and back. It is not allowed that a passenger has to walk the entire trip he or she requests, therefore constraints (23) are added, which forbid the pick up vertex and the delivery vertex to be coupled to the same point.

The next constraints update the time and passenger load at the corresponding points. First, constraints (24) are used to couple the service duration of a vertex i to the point j when vertex i is coupled to point j . This is the case when $y_{ij}^k = 1$. Let us take as an example $i = 1$. By using constraints (17) there is only one point μ coupled to vertex 1, so $y_{1\mu}^k = 1$. Because all other y_{1j}^k for $j \in \mathcal{N}$ have to be 0, $s_{1\mu}$ takes the value of the service time d_1 of vertex 1. All other s_{1j} are equal to 0. Constraints (25) do the same, but for the passenger load. If a vertex is a delivery vertex where $q_{n+i} = -q_i$, z_{ij} can also take a negative value.

For updating the time and passenger loads at all vertices in \mathcal{N} , constraints (26) and (27) are used. Constraints (26) ensure that if arc $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$ is traversed by vehicle k , then the time the vehicle arrives at vertex j is larger than or equal to the sum of the time the vehicle leaves vertex i plus the time it takes for all passengers to get in ($\sum_{l \in V} s_{li}$), plus the time it takes to travel from vertex i to vertex j (t_{ij}). The summation ($\sum_{l \in V} s_{li}$) is used because multiple pick up or delivery vertices can be coupled to the same point. Constraints (27) work in the same way, but are used for the passenger load of the vehicle. When arc (i, j) is traversed by vehicle k , the load at vertex j should be larger than or equal to the sum of the load at vertex i plus the total amount of passengers that will get in at vertex j ($\sum_{l \in V} z_{lj}$). Constraints (28) are used to ensure that the vehicle is empty when leaving and entering the depot and constraints (29) ensure that the maximal route duration T_k is not exceeded.

The time windows are incorporated in constraints (30) and (31). These constraints ensure that if a vertex $i \in P$ is coupled to point j ($y_{ij}^k = 1$), the time window $[e_i, l_i]$ is coupled to point j . Since a passenger has to walk from its origin to a point, or from a point to its destination, these time windows have to be adjusted. In constraints (30), all pick up requests are captured, where the walking time to the point is included in the time window. The time a person can be picked up at point j will be at least equal to the start time of the time window of vertex i plus the walking time from vertex i to point j . Constraints (31) capture the delivery vertices, where a person has to be dropped off at latest at the end time of the time window of vertex i , minus the time it takes to walk from point j to vertex i .

Constraints (32) and (33) ensure that the ride time remains within its boundaries. It is bounded from above by the maximum ride time L and bounded from below by the time it takes to get from the vertex where the passenger is picked up to the vertex where the passenger is dropped off. This also enforces a pick up to be carried out before a drop off. Both constraints contain two summations. The first summation takes the value of the time vehicle k arrives at the meeting point that is coupled to vertex $n+i$. The second summation takes the value of the time vehicle k leaves vertex i . This holds since constraints (16) enforce that each pick up and drop off vertex is coupled to exactly one point $j \in \mathcal{N}$, in only one vehicle. Therefore, there is at most one y_{ij}^k that is equal to 1. If this request is not served by vehicle k , both summations are equal to 0. If vehicle k serves this request, the left hand side in equation (32) and the right hand side in (33) are equal to the ride time of request i .

Constraints (34) ensure that the load of the vehicle remains within its boundaries. It can never be smaller than 0 and, when passengers get in at node j , it cannot be smaller than the number of passengers that enter at this vertex. It also never exceeds its capacity Q_k , but when passengers get out it cannot be larger than the capacity Q_k minus the number of passengers that get out of the vehicle at vertex j .

The following constraints apply to the walking distances and times of the passengers. Constraints (35) ensure that passengers do not walk more than the maximum walking distance C^{max} . The total walking time variable v_i^k is updated by constraints (36), where the walking time of pick up vertex i to point j is added to the walking time of another point to the delivery vertex $i+n$. Constraints (37) bound the total walking time of a passenger from above by the maximum walking time W .

4.5. Linearization of DARPmp

In the proposed DARPmp model, constraints (26), (27), (32) and (33) are nonlinear. For constraints (26) and (27) where the time and passenger load of the vehicle is updated, the linearization is performed by using big-M constraints, as proposed by Cordeau (2006). The new constraints can be found in formulas (41) and (42).

$$u_j^k \geq u_i^k + t_{ij} + \sum_{l \in V} s_{li} - M(1 - x_{ij}^k) \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}, k \in K \quad (41)$$

$$w_j^k \geq w_i^k + \sum_{l \in V} z_{lj} - M(1 - x_{ij}^k) \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}, k \in K \quad (42)$$

For constraints (32) and (33) that ensure the ride time of the passenger is bounded from above and below, linearizations are also necessary. This is achieved with the introduction of additional big-M inequality constraints. Constraints (43) ensure that if vertex $n+i$ is coupled to point l and vertex i is coupled to point j , the time the vehicle enters vertex l minus the time the vertex enters vertex j plus the total service time at vertex j must be smaller than the maximum ride time L . Constraints (44) do the same, but they ensure this equation is larger than the travel time from j to l .

$$u_l - M(1 - y_{i+n,l}^k) - (u_j + \sum_{i \in V} s_{ij}) - M(1 - y_{i,j}^k) \leq L \quad \forall i \in P, k \in K, j, l \in \mathcal{N} \quad (43)$$

$$t_{j,l} \leq u_l + M(1 - y_{i+n,l}^k) - (u_j + \sum_{i \in V} s_{ij}) + M(1 - y_{i,j}^k) \quad \forall i \in P, k \in K, j, l \in \mathcal{N} \quad (44)$$

After its reformulation, DARPmp is a mixed-integer linear program. The complexity of this problem is primarily dependent on the number of non-continuous variables in relation to the input size of the problem. In DARPmp, we only have binary variables, which are in different ways dependent on the input size. For the x -variable set that describes whether an arc is traversed or not, the number of variables is $|\mathcal{A}| \times |K|$. For the set of y -variables that describe to which point a vertex is coupled with for a vehicle, the number of variables is $|\mathcal{N}| \times |K| \times |V|$. The total number of binary variables for the DARPmp therefore equals to:

$$|K| \times (|\mathcal{A}| + |\mathcal{N}| \times |V|)$$

In comparison to DARP, the DARPmp has $|\mathcal{N}| \times |K| \times |V|$ additional binary variables. In addition, its binary variables are more numerous because they take values from set \mathcal{N} , which includes meeting points \mathcal{M} . Thus, computational complexity can be improved by finding intuitive ways to reduce the total number of potential meetings points while making sure that the solution quality is not compromised due to this reduction.

4.6. Preprocessing and valid inequalities

In this section, two preprocessing steps and three valid inequalities for the DARPmp are described. These preprocessing steps and valid inequalities do not remove feasible solutions from the solution space of the DARPmp model. They are able to strengthen the LP-relaxation of the model. By removing these solutions, the search process is tighter, which can result in lower computational times for solving the model.

The first preprocessing step focuses on the time windows of the requests. The corresponding pick up or delivery time window is often set to $[0, T_k]$. Using the ride time, service time and travel time, these broader time windows can be tightened. To adjust the time window related to the pick-up vertices, the new time window $e_{i,new}$ and $l_{i,new}$ are given by:

$$e_{i,new} = \max\{e_{i,old}, e_{i+n} - d_i - L\} \quad (45)$$

$$l_{i,new} = \min\{l_{i,old}, l_{i+n} - d_i - t_{i,i+n}\} \quad (46)$$

In (45) and (46), $e_{i,old} = 0$ and $l_{i,old} = T_k$. The start time window of the pick-up vertex e_i cannot be earlier than the start time window of the delivery vertex e_{i+n} , minus the maximal ride time L and the service time d_i at pick-up vertex i . The end time window of the pick-up vertex l_i cannot be later than the end time window of the delivery vertex l_{i+n} , minus the time it takes to get from the pick-up vertex to the delivery vertex $t_{i,i+n}$ minus the service time d_i at the pick-up vertex. Focusing now on the delivery vertices, the new time window $e_{i+n,new}$ and $l_{i+n,new}$ for delivery vertex $i+n$ can be obtained as follows:

$$e_{i+n,new} = \max\{e_{i+n,old}, e_i + d_i - t_{i,i+n}\} \quad (47)$$

$$l_{i+n,new} = \min\{l_{i+n,old}, l_i + d_i - L\} \quad (48)$$

In (47) and (48), $e_{i+n,old} = 0$ and $l_{i+n,old} = T_k$. The start time window of the delivery vertex e_{i+n} cannot be earlier than the start time window of the pick-up vertex e_i plus the service time at the pick-up vertex d_i and the travel time from the pick-up vertex to the delivery vertex $t_{i,i+n}$. The end time window of the delivery vertex l_{i+n} cannot be later than

the end time window of the pick-up vertex l_i plus the service time at the pick-up vertex d_i plus the maximal ride time L .

Next to the time windows of the request vertices, time windows for the meeting points can also be defined. The meeting points do not have a time window, because it is not known in advance which passenger is going to use a meeting point. However, for each meeting point, it can be defined which passengers and from which vertices can reach this meeting point. The set \mathcal{PP}_m consists of all pick up vertices that can reach meeting point m and the set \mathcal{PD}_m consists of all delivery vertices that can reach meeting point m . The set $\mathcal{E}_m = \{e_i + p_{i,m}, \forall i \in \mathcal{PP}_m\} + \{e_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{PD}_m\}$ contains all start time windows plus the walking time from the pick-up vertex to the meeting point, of all pick-up vertices that can reach meeting point m , and all the start time windows of the delivery-vertices that can reach meeting point m . The set $\mathcal{L}_m = \{l_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{PP}_m\} + \{l_i - p_{m,i}, \forall i \in \mathcal{PD}_m\}$ contains all end time windows of all vertices that can reach meeting point m . The time windows for meeting point m are then defined as follows:

$$e_m = \min(\mathcal{E}_m) \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (49)$$

$$l_m = \max(\mathcal{L}_m) \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (50)$$

The meeting point can only be reached within the time frame of the earliest possible start of a time window and the latest possible end of a time window.

The tightened time windows and the time windows for the meeting points can be used in the next preprocessing step and the first valid inequality. The next preprocessing step is the removal of infeasible arcs. If there is an arc (i, j) that has a travel time $t_{i,j}$ that is too long to reach vertex j before its time window closes, the usage of this arc will always result in an infeasible solution. Therefore, this arc is removed from the arc set. This preprocessing step is shown in (51). Arcs for which this inequality holds are removed from the arc set \mathcal{A} .

$$e_i + d_i + t_{i,j} > l_j \quad \forall (i, j) \in \mathcal{A} \quad (51)$$

The first valid inequality is adopted from Cordeau (2006) and slightly adjusted to also incorporate the meeting points. This valid inequality strengthens the bounds on the time variables and is defined as follows:

$$u_{i,k} \geq e_i + \sum_{j:(j,i) \in \mathcal{A}} \max(0, e_j - e_i + d_{min} + t_{ij}) x_{jik} \quad \forall i \in P \cup D \cup \mathcal{M}, k \in K \quad (52)$$

$$u_{i,k} \leq l_i - \sum_{j:(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} \max(0, l_i - l_j + d_{min} + t_{i,j}) x_{ijk} \quad \forall i \in P \cup D \cup \mathcal{M}, k \in K \quad (53)$$

In (52) and (53), the tightened time windows and the time windows for the meeting points are used. Parameter d_{min} is the minimal time that is necessary as service time. If multiple requests are coupled to a meeting point, this service time becomes larger. If this is the case, the right hand side of (52) becomes larger, so then the inequality still holds. For (53) the right hand side would become smaller, and thus the inequality still holds as well.

The second valid inequality removes solutions that use a sub-tour. Each vehicle traverses a number of arcs that is as large as the number of vertices present in this route, minus one. Two of the vertices in the route are always the depot and all requests should be in one of the routes. The total number of arcs that may be traversed by all vehicles in a feasible solution is at most twice the number of requests plus the number of vehicles available. When a meeting point is used for multiple requests, the number of arcs traversed in a route can only decrease. The valid inequality is displayed in (54).

$$\sum_{k \in K} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} x_{ijk} \leq 2n + |K| \quad (54)$$

Similarly, bounds on load variables w_i^k can also be strengthened as follows:

$$w_i^k \geq \max\{0, q_i\} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} \max\{0, q_j\} x_{ij} \quad (55)$$

$$w_i^k \leq \min\{Q_k, Q_k + q_i\} - (Q_k - \max_{j \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{1\}} \{q_j\} - q_i) x_{0i} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} \max\{0, q_j\} x_{ij} \quad (56)$$

Additional valid inequalities related to precedence constraints and order-matching (see [Ruland and Rodin \(1997\)](#)) can also be used for DARPmp.

4.7. Selection of meeting points

The formulation of DARPmp implies that we initially have a set of meeting points \mathcal{M} from which we need to select the optimal ones to minimize the vehicle running costs. In past DARP studies with meeting points, i.e., [Gökay \(2021\)](#), these points were pre-defined based on historical passenger demand patterns and they were necessarily part of the final solution (that is, they were all visited by the vehicles). That is, the problem was solved as a classic DARP without modifications in the problem's formulation. This, however, might result in significant optimality gaps given that the full spectrum of potential meeting points is not explored.

In our study, we developed an extended mathematical model which (a) assigns vehicles to routes, and (b) incorporates the selection of optimal meeting points to the model's formulation. To guarantee optimality, however, one should ensure that all possible meeting points in a network are taken into consideration.

Theoretically, to cover all possible meeting points in a network, there should be an infinite number of vertices \mathcal{M}' representing all points of that network. One, however, can take advantage of the maximum possible walking distance of passengers, C^{\max} , to reduce the number of potential meeting points. Knowing that passengers have pre-specified pickup and delivery locations which belong to sets P and D , respectively, each pickup $i \in P$ or delivery $j \in D$ location can have meeting points within a radius of C^{\max} . The proof of the above is trivial because if a passenger is at $i \in P$, a vehicle k is not allowed to pick him/her up from a location farther away than C^{\max} from point i . The same applies for a drop off location $j \in D$. Thus, the potential meeting points \mathcal{M}' can be reduced to the number of points within radius C^{\max} of pickup vertices P and delivery vertices D , resulting in a set $\mathcal{M}'' \subseteq \mathcal{M}'$. A description of the above is provided in [Fig.3](#). In [Fig.3](#) we have the road network of a study area. Vertices A, B, C, D, E, F are the vertices of the road network (road intersections). The lines connecting the vertices are the roads of the network. Vertices i and j are passenger pickup nodes. In this network, the possible meeting points \mathcal{M}'' lie within the two gray circles with centers the points i and j , respectively, and a radius of C^{\max} . Note that the surface area of the meeting points \mathcal{M}'' is considerably reduced compared to \mathcal{M}' which contained the entire network.

Figure 3: Depiction of the road network of a study area. The pickup vertices i and j result in a set of meeting points M'' , shown in gray color circles with radius C^{\max} .

The aforementioned reduction of potential meeting point locations establishes that, without loss of optimality, we can consider as potential meeting point locations all locations within a radius C^{\max} from every pickup point in P and delivery point in D . Notwithstanding the above, the surface area of meeting points M'' is a continuous area with infinitely many points.

To reduce the number of meeting points further without excluding any meeting points that might be part of the optimal solution, one can take advantage of the topology of the road network. Because vehicles can operate only on roads, all points of surface M'' which are outside the road sections can be excluded. That is, we have established that the potential meeting points should be part of the red lines appearing in Fig.4. These red lines are parts of the road segments which lie within the circles with center the pickup/delivery points and radius the C^{\max} distance.

Figure 4: Depiction of the road network of a study area. The pickup vertices i and j result in a set of meeting points M''' , presented by the red road segments that lie within the gray circles with the locations of the pickup points as centers and distance C^{\max} as radius.

The aforementioned observations help us to get an understanding of the total number of possible meeting points. The first critical observation is that the number of meeting points is directly related to the number of pickup and delivery vertices given that meeting points are generated within a walking distance from the locations of pickup and delivery vertices. The second observation is that the road network's structure defines the number of meeting points given that we can have meeting points only at points of the road network. For example, for

a maximum walking distance of 400 meters (Burke and Brown, 2007), a dense city network with square blocks of 80x80 meters can have inner road segments (corresponding to the red lines in Fig.4) with total length of no more than 13km. We note that in less dense areas, the total length of all road segments corresponding to a pickup or delivery point might be significantly reduced. If we analyze a dense city though, for a total road segment length of 13km we have infinitely many potential meeting points. If we discretize this space; that is, assume that meeting points should be within a distance of approx. 10 meters because otherwise they will almost overlap, we have 1300 potential meeting points for each pickup or delivery vertex. Following this simple analysis, for a dense city network with 40 pickup and delivery vertices one would probably not need to generate more than 52000 meeting points. This number might seem large, but thinking the infinitely many points that may exist in a dense city network this is already a considerable reduction.

Additional reductions to the number of possible meeting points can also occur. With the reasonable consideration that within each road segment (edge) we will have at most one pickup or delivery vertex, we can proceed to further reductions. This consideration is reasonable because in a city with edges of approx. 80 meters, it will be highly unlikely to have several pickup or delivery requests at different points of this 80-meter segment. Even if this is the case though, like in the formulation of DARP, we can assume that these passenger requests which are almost next to each other can be represented by a single pickup (or delivery) point. Let us consider again the road network of Fig.3. In this road network, we have the following edges (roads): (A,B), (A,D), (A,E), (B,C), (B,E), (B,F), (C,E), (D,E), (D,F). Let us assume, without loss of generality, that these edges are undirected (that is, the roads have lanes in both directions). Because our primary aim is to reduce the vehicle running costs, a vehicle picking up a passenger from point i can reduce its vehicle running cost the most if the passenger is picked up at its current location i or the start vertex or the end vertex of any edge within the maximum walking distance circle where point i belongs to.

The aforementioned claim can be further explained as follows. Let us assume that we have a vehicle k performing pickup and delivery activities. Let us also assume that vehicle k needs to pickup a passenger from a point i . This vehicle will not be at the edge where point i belongs to, but it will have to drive to this direction to perform the pickup. Having a meeting point inside any edge of the circle with center i and radius C^{\max} is unnecessary because this will force the vehicle to traverse this edge, increasing its running costs. Even if the vehicle has to anyway traverse an edge, having the meeting point at the start/edge of the edge will not result in an inferior solution in terms of vehicle running costs. Thus, considering only the start and end points of edges as potential meeting points reduces significantly the solution space without removing more efficient solutions from it.

This is formally proved below.

Theorem 1. *Without loss of optimality, for any pickup or delivery point i , one can consider as potential meeting points the start and end vertices of all edges that belong in a circle with center the location of point i and radius the maximum passenger walking distance C^{\max} .*

Proof. Let i be a point where a passenger needs to be picked up or delivered. Given that a passenger can walk up to C^{\max} , all points $u \in U$, where U is a circle with center the point i and radius C^{\max} , can be potential meeting points. All other meeting points outside circle U will not be used for passenger in point i because they are not within walking distance. From the infinite set of points U , a vehicle can approach only the points that belong to the road network. Let $G = (X, \Gamma)$ be the road network within circle U , where X are its vertices (road intersections), and Γ its edges (road segments between intersections), where each edge $e_j \in \Gamma$ has either a start point or an end point within circle U , or both. Each edge $e_j \in \Gamma$ has a

start point $e_j^s \in \Gamma$ and an end point $e_j^f \in \Gamma$. It follows that $e_j \in \Gamma$ if, and only if, $e_j^s \in X$ or $e_j^f \in X$, or $e_j^s \in X \wedge e_j^f \in X$.

In the edges $e_j \in \Gamma$ there are infinitely many points that can be used as meeting points for the passenger at point i . Each edge, $e_j \in \Gamma$, has also at most one pickup or delivery point. Let k be the vehicle that is ready to serve demand point i . To serve point i , vehicle k will start from another location j_k , where j_k will either be the depot, a pickup node, a delivery node or another meeting point. Whatever the location of the current point of vehicle k is, we know for sure that it is not inside the edge where point i lies ($j_k \notin e_m \setminus \{e_m^s, e_m^f\}$). Let now consider that there is a meeting point m that lies within any of the edges $e_j \in \Gamma$ and visiting it will result in a reduced vehicle running cost for vehicle k , compared to visiting any other meeting point located at the start node or the end node of every edge in Γ . By definition, meeting point m lies within an edge $e_m \in \Gamma$ which has e_m^s as its start node and e_m^f as its end node.

We consider now two cases: edge e_m is bi-directional and edge e_m is one-directional (one way street). In the former case, the shortest path of vehicle k from its current location j_k to the closest point of the edge e_m is $d(j_k, e_m)$. We note that the closest point is either the start or the end node of edge e_m . Traveling to point m will thus add running cost to vehicle k , since it will have to cover the distance $d(j_k, e_m) + d(e_m, m)$. Hence, we reached a contradiction: there is a start or end point in edge e_m which does not result in increased vehicle running costs compared to using meeting point m that lies within m . Let us now consider the case where e_m is one-directional (i.e., direction from e_m^s to e_m^f). In that case, the shortest path distance from the current location of vehicle k to m is $d(j_k, e_m^s) + d(e_m^s, m)$. Thus, we reached again a contradiction: reaching meeting point m will not result in lower running costs because there is another point, e_m^s , with running cost $d(j_k, e_m^s) \leq d(j_k, e_m^s) + d(e_m^s, m)$. \square

Exploiting the intuition of Theorem 1, one can reduce the number of meeting points to a finite set \mathcal{M} which contains all start and end points of edges that have at least one end node within a circle with radius C^{\max} and center the location of the respective pickup or delivery point. Set \mathcal{M} can be generated in polynomial time following the steps of Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Generating meeting points without excluding optimal solutions

Consider a road network with X' vertices (intersections) and Γ' edges (road segments)

Initialize Set of meeting points $\mathcal{M} = \emptyset$

for Every pickup or delivery point $i \in P \cup D$ **do**

Select vertices $X \subseteq X'$ that belong in a circle with radius C^{\max} and center i

Select edges $\Gamma \subseteq \Gamma'$ for which $e_j^s \in X$ or $e_j^f \in X$ or $e_j^s \in X \wedge e_j^f \in X$

for Every edge $e_j \in \Gamma$ **do**

if $e_j^s \notin \mathcal{M}$ **then**

Set $\mathcal{M} \leftarrow \mathcal{M} \cup \{e_j^s\}$

end if

if $e_j^f \notin \mathcal{M}$ **then**

Set $\mathcal{M} \leftarrow \mathcal{M} \cup \{e_j^f\}$

end if

end for

end for

Return set \mathcal{M}

5. Meta-heuristic Algorithms

As an extension of DARP, the DARPmp problem is NP-Hard. To solve the DARPmp for large-scale instances in short computation times, two meta-heuristic algorithms are proposed. For both algorithms, an initial solution is computed using a construction heuristic algorithm in the first step of the search. Next, this initial solution is improved using several local search operators. This section starts with an introduction about the Tabu Search meta-heuristic. Next, the construction heuristic is described, followed by a sub-section about the local search operators. Lastly, the solution evaluation procedure and the algorithmic structure of the two meta-heuristics are presented.

5.1. Tabu Search

For solving the DARPmp, a meta-heuristic Tabu Search approach is proposed. The Tabu Search method starts with an initial solution S^0 and moves at each iteration i to a new solution S' . This new solution S' is found by evaluating the neighbourhood $N(S)$ of the previous solution. The best solution in terms of the objective function value of this neighbourhood is taken as the new solution S . The neighborhood is constructed by using a local search operator, which generates solutions that contain characteristics of the current solution but are slightly different. A Tabu list is used to avoid cycling through solutions that are already known and getting trapped in a local optimum. In this list, already visited solutions are saved and the algorithm forbids to use these solutions for a certain number of iterations.

The Tabu Search algorithm was first proposed by [Glover \(1986\)](#) and was later applied to several formulations of the VRP ([Gendrau, 1994](#); [Cordeau et al., 1997](#); [Alonso et al., 2007](#)). It has also been used in several studies about the DARP. [Cordeau and Laporte \(2003\)](#) for example, use a Tabu Search approach for the static multi-vehicle DARP. [Kirchler and Calvo \(2013\)](#) use a granular Tabu Search approach for the static DARP. An improved Tabu Search heuristic for the static DARP was proposed by [Ho et al. \(2018\)](#).

Other studies use different search algorithms that also evaluate the neighborhoods of intermediate solutions. [Braekers et al. \(2014\)](#) for example, use a Deterministic Annealing framework to solve the Multi-Depot Heterogeneous DARP, which uses a threshold value to determine if a solution is accepted as the new solution. The neighborhood of this new solution is evaluated using a number of local search operators. A Genetic Algorithm is proposed by [Masmoudi et al. \(2017\)](#), which combines characteristics of known solutions to obtain better solutions. They also use local search operators to evaluate the neighborhood of these known solutions to obtain better solutions.

The proposed Tabu Search meta-heuristics of this study contain elements of the method of [Cordeau and Laporte \(2003\)](#), [Braekers et al. \(2014\)](#) and [Ho et al. \(2018\)](#). In the following sub-sections, the structure and the characteristics of the proposed methods are explained. In the first algorithm, searching for optimal meeting points is started after a solution for the DARP is found. This algorithm is referred to as TS1. In the second algorithm (TS2), searching for optimal meeting points is performed during the entire search.

5.2. Construction heuristic

As mentioned in the previous section, the Tabu Search starts with an initial solution guess to the DARPmp. [Cordeau and Laporte \(2003\)](#) use a randomly generated start solution, in which all constraints may be violated. Since the time it takes to find a first feasible solution depends on the quality of the initial solution ([Ho et al., 2018](#)), a construction heuristic that generates a solution of higher quality is proposed. Since a solution to the DARP is also feasible for the DARPmp, meeting points will not be considered in generating a start solution. Meeting points will be added later using one of the local search operators that are

explained in section 5.3. The proposed construction heuristic is similar to the heuristic used by Ho et al. (2018), but it does not use a random sequence of requests. Instead, it takes into account the direct travel distance of each request, as will be described in the remaining part of this section.

First, the requests are sorted in order of their direct travel distance, starting with the request with the largest travel distance. For each available vehicle, an empty route is constructed, containing two copies of the depot. Then, for the first request in the list, it is checked in which positions it can be inserted. It is checked whether the solution is feasible regarding the time windows, ride time, route time and passenger load. Then, the solution with the lowest cost increase is chosen. After that, the next request in the list is taken and for the solution generated in the previous step it is again checked which is the best feasible insertion position in terms of costs when inserting this request in all possible positions in all vehicles. These steps are repeated until all requests are assigned to a vehicle. If it is not possible to insert a request in any of the vehicles while the solution remains feasible, the algorithm is started over again and the request that could not be inserted is the first request to add to the routes. The other requests are added after this step, still in the order of the travel distance. The algorithmic structure is presented in Algorithm 2.

The initial solution for the second algorithm is constructed in the same way. In the next step of the algorithm, the best meeting points for this solution are found and incorporated in the solution structure.

Algorithm 2 Construction heuristic

```

Set SortedList = sort requests on travel distance
Initialize  $|K|$  routes with two copies of the depot
Assigned = False
while Assigned = False do
  for all requests in SortedList do
    for all vehicles do
      Try to insert the request in all feasible positions of the corresponding route
    end for
    Select the insertion with the lowest costs and update the solution
  end for
  if All requests are assigned then
    Assigned = True
  else
    SortedList is changed to start with the request that could not be assigned
  end if
end while

```

5.3. Local search operators

In the Tabu Search, five local search operators are used to generate a neighborhood for the current solution. The first four operators are adopted from Braekers et al. (2014) and can be applied to the original DARP formulation. The last operator is a meeting point operator that is created for the DARPmp formulation. The first four operators are called *relocate*, *exchange*, *2-opt* and *r-4-opt*, and they will be further explained in the remainder of this section. The last operator will be referred to as *meetingpoint*.

The first operator is the *relocate* operator. This operator removes a request from a randomly selected route and tries to insert it in the route of all other vehicles. It first tries to put the pick-up vertex in a feasible position. If a feasible position is found, it tries to insert the drop off vertex at a feasible location.

The second operator is the *exchange* operator. The *exchange* operator swaps a user request from one route with a user request of another route. It randomly selects a vehicle and sequentially looks at all the requests coupled to this vehicle. For these requests the best insertion position in all other routes is found by first trying to find a feasible insertion position for the pickup vertex and second a feasible insertion position for the drop off vertex. The request that is removed from one of the other vehicles is inserted in the route of the randomly selected vehicle, where the pickup and delivery vertices are inserted at the same position as they were for the request that is removed from this route.

The *2-opt* operator was first proposed by [Potvin and Rousseau \(1995\)](#) and is designed for problems with time windows. This operator takes two random routes as an input. Both routes are split in half by removing an arc where the vehicle is empty. In the next step, the operator tries to combine the first part of the first route with the second part of the second route, and vice versa. Then, it saves all feasible combinations.

The *r-4-opt* operator finds four successive arcs in a randomly selected route and removes them. The remaining parts of the route are reconnected in all possible ways. The three successive vertices that are between these arcs get a different order using this operator. While changing this order, it is taken into account that the pick up vertex of a request can never be placed after the drop off vertex of the same request in a route. All feasible orders are saved.

The last operator is the meeting point operator (*meetingpoint*), which replaces pickup or delivery vertices with meeting point vertices. For each vertex, it is determined which meeting points are close enough to walk to. For each vertex in the route, it is tried to replace the original pickup or delivery vertex with a meeting point. All feasible meeting point combinations are saved.

5.4. Solution evaluation

The aim of the Tabu Search framework is to minimize the objective function of DARPmp $f(s) = \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} c_{ij}^k x_{ij}^k$, which means the minimization of the travel costs. By applying the local search operators, different solutions with different travel costs are found. When applying local search operators to a solution and adjusting the order of vertices in certain routes, the feasibility of the passenger load, route duration, time window and ride time constraints may be affected. Evaluating the solution therefore requires to recompute the arrival time of the vehicles at each vertex, before the route duration, ride time and time window constraints can be evaluated. The arrival time at each vertex is calculated using the forward time slack method of [Cordeau and Laporte \(2003\)](#). This method uses the time windows and maximal ride time as an input and calculates if it is possible to delay the start of the service time at pickup vertices in order to still comply to the ride time and time window constraints. The procedure first minimizes the deviation from the time window constraints, then the deviation from the route duration constraints, and next sequentially minimizes the deviation from ride time constraints. Another function checks whether the passenger load is exceeded at any point of the vehicles route by keeping track of the number of passengers in the vehicle at any vertex. The construction heuristic and local search operators never create routes where the pickup vertex is inserted after the corresponding delivery vertex or routes where the pickup vertex and delivery vertex of the same request are not in the same vehicle. This ensures that these constraints will never be violated. The procedure requires a large sequence of computations. Therefore, this procedure is only used after it is first assured that the load constraint is not violated.

For the meeting point operator, it is first checked if the meeting point is close enough before it is inserted. Therefore the maximum walking distance constraints (35) are never violated. Next it is checked whether the total walking distance is not exceeded. For evaluating

the feasibility regarding the time windows, ride time and route duration, the same time slack procedure is used as mentioned before, but the time windows are adjusted beforehand to comply to constraints (30) and (31). The same method is used to check if the passenger load is exceeded at any point during the route.

5.5. Algorithm structure

Herein, the proposed structures for both Tabu Search algorithms are described. The first algorithm starts with an initial solution guess S^0 , created with the construction heuristic. The current solution S and the best found solution S^{best} is set to this initial solution. An empty list is created to save solutions that are already visited. These solutions are forbidden to evaluate. When the list reaches a maximum number of items, the solution that was first added to the list is deleted from the Tabu List.

A randomly chosen local search operator of the four operators *relocate*, *exchange*, *2-opt* or *r-4-opt* is applied to the solution S . For each solution, first the feasibility regarding the passenger load is checked, since this does not require much computation time. If the solution is feasible regarding the passenger load, its feasibility regarding the time windows, the ride time and the route time is checked.

If a feasible solution S' is found which is not already in the Tabu List, the solution with the lowest cost is chosen as the new solution S . Next, this solution is added to the Tabu List. If the costs of the new solution are lower than the cost of the current best solution S^{best} , then S^{best} will become S' . If no feasible solution is found when applying the randomly chosen operator, the current solution S will remain the same. Then, this procedure is repeated in order to explore the search space. To reduce computational costs, the algorithm keeps track of which operator in combination with which vehicle or vehicles is already performed on the current solution S and the best solution S^{best} . If no feasible neighboring solution is found using a certain combination of operator and vehicle, this combination is not applied again to the same solution, since it is already known that it will not produce feasible neighboring solutions. If no better solution is found for a number of ϕ iterations, S will get the current best solution S^{best} again, to make sure the algorithm does not keep searching in a direction where no better solutions can be found. If the algorithm has returned to the same solution S^{best} for κ times and has not found a better feasible solution, the algorithm is stopped. For the first algorithm, when the algorithm stops, a solution for the DARP has been found. To this solution, the meeting point operator is applied, which inserts meeting points that create a route with the lowest possible cost for this solution. The pseudocode of the first Tabu Search Algorithm can be found in 3.

Algorithm 3 Pseudocode for TS1

```
solution  $S^{best} \leftarrow S^0, S \leftarrow S^0$   
initialize  $counter_i \leftarrow 0, counter_s \leftarrow 0, \kappa, \phi, \text{Tabu List}$   
while  $counter_i < \kappa$  do  
    select a random local search operator  $o \in \{relocate, exchange, 2-opt, r-4-opt\}$   
    try to identify the solution with the lowest cost that is feasible and not in the Tabu  
List  
    if a solution  $S'$  is found then  
         $S \leftarrow S'$   
        if  $f(S') < f(S^{best})$  then  
             $S^{best} \leftarrow S', counter_s \leftarrow 0, counter_i \leftarrow 0$   
        end if  
    end if  
     $counter_s += 1$   
    if  $counter_s > \phi$  then  
         $S \leftarrow S^{best}, counter_i \leftarrow counter_i + 1$   
    end if  
end while  
for all possible meeting points do  
    apply meeting point operator to  $S^{best}$  and find best solution with meeting points  $S_{mp}^{best}$   
end for  
return  $S_{mp}^{best}$ 
```

The structure of the second algorithm is almost the same as the structure of the first algorithm. It also starts with the initial solution generated with the construction heuristic and has a Tabu List in which the solutions that are already visited are saved. The same local search operators are applied to the current S in a random order. The difference is that in each iteration, for each neighborhood generated using the local search operators, it is checked if from this solution a feasible solution using meeting points can be generated. The solution with the lowest costs for the meeting point route is then selected. If no better solution is found for a number of ϕ iterations, S will get the current best solution S^{best} again. If the algorithm has returned to the same solution S^{best} for κ times and has not found a better feasible solution in the meantime, the algorithm is stopped. No extra operations are performed on this final solution. The algorithmic structure of the second Tabu Search Algorithm is presented in 4.

Algorithm 4 Pseudocode for TS2

```
solution  $S^{best} \leftarrow S_0, S \leftarrow S^0$   
initialize  $counter_i \leftarrow 0, counter_s \leftarrow 0, \kappa, \phi$  Tabu List  
while  $counter_i < \kappa$  do  
    select a random local search operator  $o \in \{relocate, exchange, 2-opt, r-4-opt\}$   
    apply meeting point operator to all solutions in neighborhood  
    try to identify the solution with the lowest cost that is feasible and not in the Tabu  
    List  
    if a solution  $S'$  is found then  
         $S \leftarrow S'$   
        if  $f(S') < f(S^{best})$  then  
             $S^{best} \leftarrow S', counter_s \leftarrow 0, counter_i \leftarrow 0$   
        end if  
    end if  
     $counter_s \leftarrow counter_s + 1$   
    if  $counter_s > \phi$  then  
         $S \leftarrow S^{best}, counter_i \leftarrow counter_i + 1$   
    end if  
end while  
return  $S^{best}$ 
```

6. Numerical Experiments

In this section, the results of the numerical experiments using both the Branch-and-cut algorithm and the two versions of the Tabu Search are presented. First, the formulation is demonstrated in a toy network. Next, two types of experiments are performed that have a different aim. In the first experiment, the aim is to give an insight in the influence of the valid inequalities and the preprocessing steps on the computational performance of the Branch-and-cut algorithm. In the second experiment, the Branch-and-cut algorithm and both Tabu Search algorithms are applied to a set of benchmark instances, with the aim to give insight in the computational performance of all algorithms.

In the first sub-section, the demonstration using the toy network is presented. In the second sub-section, details about the data and the used resources are described. In the following sub-sections, the experiments are presented in the same order as they are presented in this introduction. Each sub-section starts with a more detailed description of the experiment and its experimental design, followed by the results and their interpretation.

6.1. Demonstration in a toy network

To validate the DARPmp, a toy network is created to test the new formulation. This toy network is displayed in Figure 5. This problem instance has 8 trip requests, thus $P = \{1, 2, \dots, 8\}$ and $D = \{9, 10, \dots, 16\}$. The set with additional vertices that can be used as meeting points is $\mathcal{M} = \{18, 19, \dots, 31\}$ and they are all end points of directed or undirected edges. The depots are vertices 0 and 17. There are 2 vehicles available ($K = \{0, 1\}$) with capacity $Q_k = 3$ and maximum tour duration of $T_k = 300$. The maximal tolerable ride time for a passenger is $L = 30$. For each pick up request, one person wants to enter the vehicle ($q_i = 1$ for $i \in P$) and at each drop off, one person wants to exit ($q_i = -1$ for $i \in D$). Each vertex has associated time windows. The service duration for each passenger equals 3, ($d_i = 3$ for $i \in V$). The maximal walking distance is $C^{max} = 0.75$. The maximum total walking distance is $W = 10$. Two tests are performed on this toy network in order to compare the formulations. First, the original DARP is implemented to this network. Next,

the DARPmp is implemented to the toy network with the additional set of meeting points \mathcal{M} .

Figure 5: Toy network used to implement DARP and DARPmp and illustrate their differences

For applying the original DARP to the toy network, the meeting point vertices are not taken into consideration since this formulation does not contain meeting points. The formulation presented in Formulas (1) to (15) is used to solve the instance. The solution can be found in Figure 6. Two routes are generated, where the blue route represents vehicle 0 and the green route represents vehicle 1. The specifications of the route of vehicle 0 are presented in Table 2 and those of vehicle 1 are presented in Table 3. In these tables, the load at every vertex w_i^k and the time the vehicle arrives at each vertex u_i^k are given, together with the corresponding time windows. The total vehicle travel costs for this instance are 101.46.

Figure 6: DARP solution for the toy network

Table 2: DARP: Route of vehicle 0 in toy network

i	d \rightarrow	6 \rightarrow	7 \rightarrow	5 \rightarrow	15 \rightarrow	8 \rightarrow	14 \rightarrow	13 \rightarrow	16 \rightarrow	d
w_i^0	0	1	2	3	2	3	2	1	0	0
e_i	0	20	20	20	60	50	80	80	100	0
u_i^0	0	47	50.8	56.7	70	73.6	80	89.7	106.6	300
l_i	300	80	80	80	100	150	100	100	130	300

used. The total travel costs for this instance when applying the DARPmp are 96.14, which are lower than the costs for the DARP (101.46). In fact, the use of meeting points resulted in a 5.24% decrease of the total travel costs.

Table 4: DARPmp: Route of vehicle 0 in toy network

j	d \rightarrow	20 \rightarrow	26 \rightarrow	25 \rightarrow	19 \rightarrow	3 \rightarrow	21 \rightarrow	12 \rightarrow	d
i	0	1	2	10	9	3	11,4	12	17
w_j^0	0	1	2	1	0	1	1	0	0
e_j	0	53	53	100	100	70	120	150	0
u_j^0	0	59.9	81.9	100.0	110.1	145.9	157.2	170.9	300
l_j	300	150	130	127.2	147.1	160	157.2	180	300

Table 5: DARPmp: Route of vehicle 1 in toy network

j	d \rightarrow	5 \rightarrow	15 \rightarrow	30 \rightarrow	13 \rightarrow	31 \rightarrow	d
i	0	5, 6, 7	15, 8	14	13	16	17
w_j^1	0	3	3	2	1	0	0
e_j	0	22.8	60	80	80	100	0
u_j^1	0	48.1	67.3	80	87.1	100	300
l_j	300	80	100	100	97.2	127.2	300

6.2. Benchmark instances and experimentation setup

To evaluate the Branch-and-cut algorithm and the two versions of the Tabu Search, various experiments are performed on the benchmark network instances of <http://neumann.hec.ca/chairedistributique/data/darp/branch-and-cut/>. The benchmark instances vary from 2 to 4 vehicles and from 16 to 48 trip requests. They all have 1 passenger per trip request. In order to use these benchmark instances, they first have to be adjusted to contain meeting points. The adjusted benchmark instances can be found at <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/h5392z6csr/1>. For all of these instances, $C^{max} = 0.53$.

For all experiments, a conventional computing machine with a AMD Ryzen 7 PRO 5850U processor (1.90 GHz) and 16GB of RAM is used. The Branch-and-cut algorithm is implemented using Gurobi's version 9.5.2 in Python 3.9, which uses a series of cutting planes (i.e., Gomory cuts, Clique, Set cover, GUB cover, MIR). The Tabu Search algorithms are programmed and implemented in Python 3.9. For this model, several parameters are used. These are described in section 5.5. For the first TS algorithm, the number of iterations ϕ after which S returns back to S^{best} is set to 50. The number of iterations after which no better solution is found and the algorithm is terminated is set to 250. This means that κ is set to 5. For the second TS algorithm, ϕ is set to 10 because observing the algorithm's search revealed that it did not often find a better solution when it was not within 10 iterations. For this algorithm, κ is set to 10. This means that the algorithm is terminated if no better solution was found for 100 iterations.

6.3. The effect of preprocessing steps and valid inequalities

The first experiment focuses on the preprocessing steps and valid inequalities described in section 4.6, and their effect on the computational performance of the Branch-and-cut algorithm. The first preprocessing step is the time window tightening (P1), the second preprocessing step is the removal of infeasible arcs (P2), the first valid inequality is tightening the bounds on the service time variable (V1), the second is the sub-tour elimination constraint (V2), and the third is tightening the bounds on the load variables (V3). In order to evaluate their effects, the smallest benchmark instance with 2 vehicles and 16 trip requests is used.

For the sake of experimentation, 17 instances are created with the number of meeting points varying from 0 to 16. For the analysis, 10 different experiments are performed. P2 and V1 are always tested in combination with P1, because P2 and V1 use the time windows as an input, and P1 already tightens those time windows. Furthermore, every combination of preprocessing steps and valid inequalities is tested. The model is run for a maximum of 3600 seconds. If the optimal solution is not found after 3600 seconds, the model is cut off. The expectation is that each preprocessing step and each valid inequality has an influence on the computational time and that all four combined results in the lowest computation times.

Table 6 shows the computational results of the 10 different combinations of preprocessing steps and valid inequalities. When trying to solve the model with no preprocessing steps and valid inequalities applied, the run time takes over 3600 seconds for every instance. This also holds for models where only P1 or P1 and P2 are applied. For all other combinations of preprocessing steps and valid inequalities that are tested, the optimal solution is found for all of the instances within 3600 seconds. The run time increases as the number of meeting points increases, with some minor exceptions.

Table 6: Computational performance in seconds (s) for different sets of preprocessing steps (P) and valid inequalities (V), on instances with different numbers of meeting points (MP)

MP	Without	P1	P1&P2	V2	P1&V2	P1&V1	P1,P2&V1	P1,P2&V2	P1&V1,V2	P1,P2&V1,V2,V3
0	-	-	-	23.89	39.22	5.79	5.60	31.12	5.23	5.22
1	-	-	-	83.85	45.44	6.61	5.91	27.04	6.12	5.79
2	-	-	-	48.01	35.25	6.77	6.51	26.84	6.04	5.93
3	-	-	-	137.29	55.34	7.02	7.21	32.25	7.02	6.81
4	-	-	-	120.57	31.33	7.66	7.17	31.01	6.62	6.68
5	-	-	-	76.63	51.68	8.25	8.98	40.98	7.34	6.85
6	-	-	-	246.40	53.57	13.74	14.66	42.80	7.73	9.18
7	-	-	-	290.44	170.12	23.98	15.22	44.96	8.46	8.33
8	-	-	-	391.29	69.18	17.46	19.64	46.87	10.21	9.33
9	-	-	-	328.68	165.81	22.44	22.69	64.33	10.51	10.19
10	-	-	-	275.84	64.48	65.99	71.18	49.75	11.81	9.59
11	-	-	-	750.42	96.87	52.72	102.51	70.95	11.13	10.87
12	-	-	-	2268.32	104.96	143.92	63.96	59.87	12.66	13.25
13	-	-	-	673.99	219.45	92.30	81.31	68.01	11.67	11.26
14	-	-	-	590.29	106.49	136.17	95.58	65.44	12.79	12.60
15	-	-	-	820.91	189.87	161.69	134.37	73.01	15.29	13.13
16	-	-	-	1375.30	140.76	98.80	118.89	80.94	19.74	14.22

Investigating the influence of the preprocessing steps and valid inequalities on the run times, it is observed that P1 on its own does not keep the run time below 3600 s. However, in combination with other preprocessing steps and valid inequalities it does have an effect. When comparing the run time for the experiment with V2 only and the experiment with P1 and V2, the run times drop significantly when incorporating P1 too. It does seem plausible that this valid inequality does not have a large effect on its own, because it only affects the wider time windows of the vertices.

For P2, the impact on the run time is less noticeable. Concerning the experiment with P1 and V1 and the experiment with P1, P2 and V1, the differences in run times are minor. On the other hand, the difference between the experiments with P1 and V2 and the experiments with P1, P2 and V2, P2 seems to be more noticeable. The run time especially decreases for the instances with more meeting points. When comparing the experiment where P1, V1 and V2 are used to the experiment with all valid inequalities, the results look similar. However, most of the run times are slightly lower when P2 is used as well. It seems that P2 mainly has an effect on the instances with a larger number of meeting points. A larger number of meeting points means that there are more arcs, so also possibly more arcs that are infeasible and can be removed. This can explain why this step mainly affects instances with more meeting points. The observation that the preprocessing step itself does not have

a large effect on the run time might be explained by not having many arcs that are infeasible due to the time windows.

V1 seems to have a large effect on the run time. When comparing the experiment where only P1 and V2 are used to the experiment where P1, V1 and V2 are used, it can be observed that the run time decreases significantly for all instances. When comparing the experiment with P1, P2 and V2 to the experiments where all valid inequalities are used, it is again visible that the run time decreases significantly when V1 is used. This effect is especially visible for the instances with a larger number of meeting points. The large impact on the run time can be explained by the valid inequality being able to cut off a larger number of infeasible solutions than P1 and P2. This valid inequality is bounding the service time of all vertices, which has more potential than only removing infeasible arcs.

Lastly, we explore the effect of V2. Applying only this valid inequality already results in solving all instances within 3600 seconds. When comparing the experiment with P1 and V1 to the experiment with P1, V1 and V2, it can be observed that V2 has the largest effect on the run time for the instances with a larger number of meeting points. The same holds when comparing the experiment with P1, P2 and V1 and the experiment with all valid inequalities. The valid inequality puts a bound on the number of x -variables, which means that it puts a bound on the number of arcs that can be traversed. The number of arcs is higher in the instances with more meeting points, which can be an explanation for the observation that V2 mainly has an effect on the instances with more meeting points.

As expected, a pattern of higher run times for a higher number of meeting points is observed. However, there are some instances where this pattern does not hold. An example is for the experiment where P1 and V2 are applied and the instance with 7 meeting points has a run time of 170.12 seconds whereas the instance with 8 meeting points has a run time of 69.18 seconds. These fluctuations in run times have an explanation. When adding a meeting point to the graph, the input sets of the problem become larger and the number of variables increases. The expectation is that the run time is larger in this case. However, adding a different input to the model can sometimes also alter the initial conditions for the Branch-and-bound algorithm, resulting in a more favourable starting position and finding an optimal solution faster.

The findings are in line with the expectations that are mentioned in the first part of this section. Each preprocessing step or valid inequality has an influence on the run time and the run times are the lowest when all preprocessing steps and valid inequalities are used. Overall, the run time increases as the number of meeting points increases, with the exceptions that are discussed in the previous part of this section. All preprocessing steps or valid inequalities that are applied in this work are also used in other research regarding vehicle routing problems and specifically in research regarding the DARP (Cordeau, 2006; Masmoudi et al., 2018; Bongiovanni et al., 2019). The observation that using these preprocessing steps and valid inequalities results in lower run times for the Branch-and-cut algorithm of the DARPmp validates their usefulness.

6.4. Computational results for large-scale instances

Herein, the computational performance of the Branch-and-cut algorithm without preprocessing steps and valid inequalities (B&C), the Branch-and-cut algorithm with preprocessing steps and valid inequalities (B&C PV) and both the Tabu Search algorithms (TS1 and TS2) are tested on larger instances. For this comparison, all aforementioned instances with 2 to 4 vehicles and 16 to 48 trip requests are used. The Branch-and-cut algorithms are run one time per benchmark instance and both Tabu Search algorithms are run five times per benchmark instance to obtain the results. The Tabu Search algorithms are run five times because the outcome for both the objective function value and the run time can differ significantly due

to the randomness (stochastic exploration nature) of the Tabu Search metaheuristic. The a priori expectation is that the run times of B&C will be higher than the run times of B&C PV. Next to that, it is expected that B&C PV will be faster for smaller instances than TS1 and TS2, but that it will become slower than TS1 and TS2 when the benchmark instances have more vehicles and more trip requests. Furthermore, it is expected that TS1 produces solutions faster than TS2 but that the resulting routes have higher costs. For TS2, it is expected that it produces solutions slower than TS1 due to the application of the meeting point operator in every iteration, but that the resulting routes have lower costs.

In Table 7 the computational results of B&C, B&C PV and TS1 and TS2 are presented. In the first column, the instances are presented in a format that represents the number of vehicles, the number of trip request and the number of meeting points. For example the instance in the first row, has 2 vehicles, 16 trip requests and 24 meeting points. Furthermore, the table presents for both Branch-and-cut versions the best objective function value (OFV) when the solver was terminated, the optimality gap (OG) considering the difference between the OFV and the lower bound, and the run time in seconds. When OG is equal to 0, the respective solution of the Branch-and-Cut versions is optimal. Table entries with the term N/A indicate that the Branch-and-Cut algorithm was not able to compute a feasible solution within the time duration of the optimization run and the OG was thus not established. For both Tabu Search algorithms, (i) the best found objective function value (OFV), (ii) the gap between this best found objective function value and the objective function value found with the Branch-and-cut algorithm (Gap), (iii) the average objective function value of all runs (AVG), and (iv) the average run time in seconds are presented. We finally note that the B&C implementations use cutting planes. As an example, the cutting planes used by the B&C PV implementation in Gurobi when solving the instance a2-16-24 were the following: Gomory: 30, Cover: 89, Implied bound: 24, Projected implied bound: 1, Clique: 15, MIR: 26, Flow cover: 185, Inf proof: 22, Zero half: 180, Mod-K: 1, RLT: 15, Relax-and-lift: 6.

Table 7: Computational results of the Branch-and-cut algorithm without preprocessing and valid inequalities, the Branch-and-cut algorithm with preprocessing and valid inequalities, Tabu Search algorithm 1, and Tabu Search algorithm 2

Instance	B&C			B&C PV			TS1				TS2			
	OFV	OG	Time (s)	OFV	OG	Time (s)	OFV	Gap	AVG	Time (s)	OFV	Gap	AVG	Time (s)
a2-16-24	302.17	22.1%	15000	285.53	0%	30.77	286.57	0.361%	286.57	31.71	286.57	0.361%	288.41	160.66
a2-20-30	379.61	41.7%	15000	337.62	0%	74.53	337.62	0.000%	337.62	139.09	337.62	0.000%	337.62	1050.51
a2-24-36	491.16	43.8%	15000	423.15	0%	134.65	423.53	0.090%	425.29	157.14	423.20	0.011%	424.88	918.83
a3-18-27	352.36	89.3%	15000	295.20	0%	2414.48	295.21	0.003%	299.53	22.42	301.81	2.240%	302.70	77.40
a3-24-36	489.12	76.4%	15000	336.57	0%	14036.27	342.12	1.650%	342.99	154.63	341.13	1.354%	343.83	692.67
a3-30-45	N/A	N/A	15000	497.26	13.1%	15000	486.13	-	486.94	210.40	486.42	-	491.90	1112.18
a3-36-54	N/A	N/A	15000	649.71	32.6%	15000	583.38	-	584.52	328.55	556.94	-	559.73	3226.27
a4-16-24	N/A	N/A	15000	382.12	98.3%	15000	276.32	-	279.44	14.07	276.32	-	279.46	38.20
a4-24-36	N/A	N/A	15000	452.12	84.6%	15000	369.18	-	378.66	66.13	375.61	-	379.83	251.16
a4-32-48	N/A	N/A	15000	N/A	N/A	15000	478.02	-	486.93	138.21	475.46	-	494.11	740.74
a4-40-60	N/A	N/A	15000	N/A	N/A	15000	561.28	-	565.22	421.38	562.30	-	568.96	2239.43
a4-48-72	N/A	N/A	15000	N/A	N/A	15000	675.10	-	685.48	850.51	676.42	-	680.51	9051.69

It can be observed that none of the instances can be solved to optimality with Branch-and-cut algorithm without using the preprocessing steps and valid inequalities. When applying all preprocessing steps and valid inequalities, the first five instances can be solved. The run time increases as the instance gets more trip requests and more vehicles, which is something that is also observed in other research (Cordeau, 2006; Bongiovanni et al., 2019). Both Tabu Search algorithms were able to find a feasible solution for all the instances. Expectedly, the run times for both Tabu Search algorithms seem to increase as the number of trip requests increases. They do not seem to increase as the number of vehicles increases. The run time for a4-16-24 is, for example, lower than the run time for a2-16-24. However, this pattern is also observed for other meta-heuristics using variants of the same instances (Braekers et al., 2014; Malheiros et al., 2021).

When comparing B&C PV with TS1, it can be observed that B&C PV produces slightly better results in terms of the objective function value. Only for the instance a2-20-30, the

same solution is found. For the other instances, TS1 produces results with a gap ranging from 0.003% to 1.650%. TS1 only visits solutions that are feasible for the DARP, to which in the last step the meeting point operator is applied. For the instances with a gap larger than 0%, the solution that is found by B&C PV is infeasible for the DARP, if the incorporated meeting points are translated back to their original pickup and delivery vertices. Therefore, the optimal solution is not found using TS1 and a gap between the result using B&C PV and TS1 remains. Regarding the run time, B&C PV produces results faster than TS1 for the smaller instances. For the larger instances, TS1 is faster. The run time of TS1 increases as the number of trip requests increases. These findings are in line with the expectations mentioned in the beginning of this section.

When comparing B&C PV with TS2, B&C PV produces better results regarding the objective function value. Only for the instance a2-20-30 the same objective function value is found. TS2 algorithm produces results for the other instances with a gap between 0.011% and 2.240%. TS2 is able to visit solutions that are infeasible for the DARP, resulting in a lower gap for instances a2-24-36 and a3-24-36 compared to TS1. However, TS2 does still not find the optimal solution. It might be that the operators used are not the best for this particular problem, or that not enough iterations are performed. Looking at the run time, B&C PV is faster for the first three instances, but TS2 is faster for the two instances with 3 vehicles. For most of the instances the run time increases as the number of trip requests increases, except for the instance a2-20-30, which has a higher average run time than the instance a2-24-36. These findings are in line with the expectations set in the first part of this section.

When comparing TS1 and TS2 regarding the best found objective function value, the results are similar. For 3 instances, the same solution was found as the best solution. For 5 instances, TS1 finds a better solution and for 4 instances TS2 finds a better solution. For most instances, the difference is not larger than 7. The biggest difference in run time is for the instance a3-36-54, where the difference is 26.44 and TS2 performs better. Exploring the average values, there is one instance for which algorithms have the same average, 8 instances for which the average of TS1 is lower and 3 instances for which the average of TS2 is lower. Comparing the two algorithms in terms of run time, TS1 is on average 5 times faster for each instance than TS2. These findings are not completely in line with the expectations set in the first part of this section. It was expected that the run times for TS2 would be higher than the run times for TS1, but that TS2 would produce better results than TS1. There are several reasons that might explain why TS2 does not find better results than TS1. The first reason could be that TS2 is cut off when no better solution is found for 100 iterations, while TS1 is cut off when no better solution has been found for 250 iterations. However, if the stopping criterion for TS2 was also set to 250 iterations, the run times of TS2 would have increased even more. The second explanation could be that the solution space is searched differently in TS2. It does not follow the pattern of feasible DARP solutions, but of feasible DARPmp solutions. It could be that once a solution that is infeasible for the DARP is found, it is difficult to get a better feasible solution in the next steps.

Finally, in Table 8 we present the objective function values of the optimal solutions of DARPmp and the optimal solutions of DARP for benchmark instances of up to 24 requests. In the last column, the percentage improvement of the total vehicle running costs (VRC) when adopting the DARPmp approach is presented.

Table 8: Computational results of DARPmp and DARP

Instance	OFV DARPmp	OFV DARP	VRC improvement
a2-16	285.53	294.25	2.97%
a2-20	337.62	344.83	2.10%
a2-24	423.15	431.12	1.85%
a3-18	295.20	300.48	1.76%
a3-24	336.57	344.83	1.76%

7. Conclusion

The aim of this research is to extend the DARP with the inclusion of optimal meeting points. This is achieved by formulating a mixed-integer linear program with preprocessing steps and valid inequalities and two meta-heuristics to find solutions for the DARPmp. This study showed that preprocessing steps and valid inequalities can be used to improve the computational performance of the DARPmp. Two Tabu Search frameworks were proposed to approximate the optimal solution for the DARPmp. The first algorithm finds solutions with an optimality gap ranging from 0% to 1.65%. The run times for this algorithm range from 14.07 seconds to 850.51 seconds. The second algorithm finds solutions with an optimality gap ranging from 0% to 2.24% and has run times ranging from 38.20 to 9051.69 seconds.

For further research, the possibility of incorporating more preprocessing steps and valid inequalities that are feasible for the DARPmp can be explored. There are valid inequalities and preprocessing steps that are used for the DARP or other types of VRPs. [Cordeau \(2006\)](#), for example, uses inequalities that bound the load variables w_i^k , capacity constraints, precedence constraints and generalized order constraints as valid inequalities for the DARP. These can possibly be adapted to hold for the DARPmp as well.

Next, it could also be interesting to use other objective functions in the DARPmp and compare the effects on performance indicators like the total travel costs and detours for the passengers. Other objective function attributes that could be considered are the minimization of the inconvenience for passengers, minimizing the vehicle emissions, minimizing the empty-vehicle kilometres, optimizing the passenger occupancy rate and the matching of passengers in the same vehicle.

Finally, the effect of other local search operators and other meta-heuristics to approximate the optimal solution of the DARPmp can be explored. Meta-heuristics that are used for other versions of the DARP are, for example, Genetic Algorithms ([Masmoudi et al., 2017](#)), Deterministic Annealing ([Bräysy et al., 2014](#)) and Variable Neighborhood Search ([Parragh et al., 2010](#)). In our work, we used Tabu search metaheuristics with five local search operators. Although the structure of these Tabu search methods provide a first direction on how to incorporate meeting points in the metaheuristics' structures, more metaheuristics can be developed to improve further the ability to obtain well-performing solutions in larger problem instances.

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